

Hope Is On The Horizon

By- Ayush Yadav, 07/10/2020

A recent clinical trial and study of the Moderna's Vaccine candidate **mRNA-1273** shows encouraging results on the safety and effectiveness of the touted vaccine, making it shine as a beacon of hope for 'millions' round the globe hoping for a return of things back to the way they were before the Coronavirus pandemic. The clinical trial for the vaccine was sponsored by National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) which also co-developed the vaccine mRNA-1273 with Moderna in Cambridge, Massachusetts; while the study using the data from the clinical trial was published in New England Journal of Medicine by Authors- Evan J. Anderson (M.D.), Nadine G. Rouphael, (M.D.), Alicia T. Widge (M.D.), Lisa A. Jackson (M.D., M.P.H), *et al.* Since this was a phase-1 clinical trial, the study focused on which dose of the vaccine is best in terms of both immunogenicity and safety. Also, for the first time mRNA-1273 vaccine data is available for people above the age of 56 years.

The vaccine comprises of mRNA molecule which has genetic information to make spike proteins(Spike Glycoprotein Trimer, S-2P) which are present on the surface of SARS COV-2 thus mimicking as if the virus was actually present in the body. The mRNA particle is encapsulated in lipid nanoparticles and in a normal saline solution to reach the target vaccine concentrations. The vaccine is given through intramuscular injections in the arm (Deltoid). A similar phase-1 clinical trial and study of the vaccine at 25,100 and 250 micrograms of vaccine was done for the age group of 18 to 55 years of age and was found considerably effective and safe for them, but this time the study focuses on using the same candidate vaccine for old people, i.e. above the age of 56 years and to get a safe and effective vaccine dosage for them. This is crucial since **old age people account for majority of deaths due to Covid-19 disease.**

The trial was conducted on 40 people above the age of 56 years. They then divided the study group into 4 subgroups of 10 participants according to participants age and the dosage of vaccine to be given to them. They were- 1. Participant Age 56-70 years and dosage 25 micrograms of vaccine, 2. Participant Age 56-70 years and dosage 100 micrograms of vaccine, 3. Participant Age 71 years or above and dosage 25 micrograms, 4. Participant Age 71 years or above and dosage 100 micrograms. Each subgroup was given vaccine on day 1 and day 29 and assay for antibodies and T cell response was done through different methods like ELISA(Enzyme linked Immunosorbent assay), Live Virus neutralization assays and Intracellular Cytokine-staining assay on day 7 and 14 after each vaccination and also on day 57. One noteworthy point was that almost all of **the study population was white American males and females with exception of 2 participants.** The results generated from the above trial were analysed then.

The data was compared with a control of participants(18-55 years) who had received convalescent plasma therapy to calculate their levels of antibodies, So that the study also compares whether the vaccine generates a higher immune response than plasma therapy or not. After the statistics of vaccine trial were compared it showed that indeed the level of antibodies against SARS COV-2 virus was more in the **vaccine trial group than in the plasma therapy group**, such that the 71years of age and 100 micrograms vaccine group's(GMT-1,128,391) neutralizing antibody levels far exceeded that of plasma therapy group (GMT-138,901); here GMT means the geometric mean titer level of antibody. Immune response was also seen in terms of response of Type 1 T-helper cells (also called CD4 cells) against the spike protein, it was observed that 100 microgram dosage was important for inducing T helper cell response in participants older than 71 years of age, while 25 micrograms group initiated a weaker response than the 100 micrograms dosage group. Data on long term durability of immunogenicity is not available for mRNA-1273 vaccine but the authors have mentioned that they will follow up the antibody concentration levels in participants for 12 months since day 1 of vaccination.

The vaccine was deemed safe by authors as the data showed that the participants experienced only mild or moderate, local and systemic adverse events which were of short duration and happened mostly after a second dose of vaccine. After the second dose of vaccine the symptoms usually observed were fever, headache, fatigue, myalgia (muscle pain) , redness at injection site and swelling at injection site. Moderate adverse events were rare, but one participant reported reduced appetite. One thing to note is that fever is present in both 1st vaccine dosage as well as in 2nd dosage. **No Severe adverse events related to the vaccine were reported by any of the participants.** These findings are encouraging and will help in public acceptance of the vaccine as people are getting polarized and having doubts on safety of vaccines due to many conspiracy theories floating around biomedical corporations.

Limitations of the study were also evident, since this is a phase-1 trial which mainly ascertains the safest level of vaccine on a small group of participants which is 40 in this trial, we do not have data to ascertain trends in a larger population. Also from an Indian perspective this mRNA vaccine may have different immune response in Asian populations because the trial data was predominantly for white males and females, almost no Ethnic diversity. Another fact to note is that Age alone is not a factor determining poor immune responses in individuals as people with chronic diseases (Hypertension, Diabetes, etc.)have an impaired immune system which might render the vaccine useless. Nevertheless the findings are proof enough that the vaccine trial can move forward to other phases of clinical trial which will have a larger study population and more ethnic diversity to determine it efficacy as a saviour globally, also we have to determine whether this vaccine is affordable for all or not and whether it can be mass produced quickly. If successful then this vaccine will save many lives and help cease lockdowns around the world, but as a crucial step has been achieved in the form phase-1 trials for this vaccine, we can now say that '**Hope is on the Horizon**'.

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Original Article and Article link from NEJM

Safety and Immunogenicity of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA-1273 Vaccine in Older Adults

